

Standardizing Machine Learning APIs for Earth Observation Data Cubes

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Abstract. The accessibility of satellite data has catalyzed the hosting of these data sets in cloud computing environments, leading to several Earth Observation (EO) cloud platforms with analytical capabilities. However, transitioning between these platforms remains a challenge. The openEO specification addresses this by unifying backend services to be accessed via REST protocol using R, Javascript, and Python clients, yet it lacks a stable machine learning (ML) specification. This vision paper proposes extending the openEO API by developing a ML Application Programming Interface (API) specification for EO data cubes to facilitate ML models' reproducibility, reusability, and interoperability in multiple backend services and federated cloud platforms. Our efforts focus on establishing protocols for data pre-processing, model training, model parameter tuning, model prediction, model saving, and loading of existing models, facilitating the use of classical ML and deep learning (DL) algorithms for critical applications such as environmental monitoring and disaster response. Future efforts will focus on implementing this ML specification across multiple EO backend services and cataloging spatio-temporal ML models.

Keywords: EO data cubes · machine learning · deep learning · GeoAI · interoperability · openEO.

1 Introduction

Advancements in Satellite technology have enabled our global understanding of Earth by collecting extensive data on its surface, atmosphere, and oceans. Recently, more open governmental data-sharing policies have facilitated wider access to these large datasets [1], so that both the public and the scientific community can utilize them for environmental monitoring and to deepen our understanding of global phenomena such as food security, health, carbon biomass assessment, land cover mapping, and disaster management [2]. Consequently, this data is increasingly being hosted on cloud computing environments which has led to the development of several Earth Observation (EO) cloud computing platforms [3] such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) [4] and Sentinel Hub¹, enabling users to access, process and analyze large scale Earth observation data [3].

¹ <https://www.sentinel-hub.com/>

However, transitioning between these EO cloud platforms remains a challenge as they have different API interfaces, and different underlying complex software architectures, some are proprietary software and they have different EO data collections. This hinders reproducibility and interoperability in cloud-based EO data analysis, which are key concepts that are being adopted in the scientific community to advance research and collaboration. The concept of "research reproducibility" involves obtaining the same results as those reported in a scientific paper by using identical source code and data [5]. Recommendations to address technical issues that hinder reproducibility include embedding library versions in the source code, writing encapsulating code, running code in clean environments like the Docker container, and sharing code and data in their original forms [6]. Additionally, creating reproducible workflows is suggested to achieve reproducibility in Geography and Geosciences [7].

The concept of "interoperability" is defined by Wegner [8] as "the ability of two or more software components to cooperate despite differences in language, interface, and execution platform". Wagemann [9] conducted a survey of 231 users of big Earth data, finding that about 90 % of the respondents identified "interoperability of data and data systems" as the most crucial aspect of data analysis.

The openEO specification [10], addresses the challenges of reproducibility and interoperability in EO cloud-based backends by standardizing how backend services are accessed irrespective of the underlying software architecture. It utilizes the Representational State Transfer (REST) protocol and the OpenAPI specification². It has Python, R, Javascript, and Julia clients — the first three being the top three programming languages favored by Big Earth data users, with Python and R being the dominant [9]. The openEO ecosystem uses the SpatioTemporal Assets Catalog (STAC)³ specification for search and discovery of EO data, and data cubes as multidimensional arrays for representing satellite image time series. It has several backend implementations, such as the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem⁴, and the federated openEO Platform⁵.

Although openEO has advanced reproducibility and interoperability, it lacks a stable machine learning (ML) specification, which limits its adoption to Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI) tasks. This shortcoming hinders users from leveraging ML techniques that are increasingly important in a variety of geospatial applications, reducing openEO's appeal for broader, more complex ML-driven geospatial analysis.

Data cubes can be viewed as tensor representations, simplifying the application of ML algorithms such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and related architectures [11]. Recent years have seen the emergence of ML algorithms like TempCNN [14], ConvLSTM [13], Temporo-Spatial Vision Transformer (TSViT) [17], spatial-spectral-temporal neural network (SSTNN) [18],

² <https://swagger.io/specification/>

³ <https://stacspec.org/en>

⁴ <https://openeo.dataspace.copernicus.eu/openeo/1.2>

⁵ <https://openeo.cloud>

Fig. 1. A typical raster data cube comprises four dimensions: x, y, bands, and time. Source (Pebesma and Bivand [19])

and Temporal Self-Attention [12] that can be used to derive value from EO data cubes. Moreover, there is a need for easy search and discovery of ML models for EO data cubes [16], particularly models that are beneficial to communities with limited resources such as computing access and internet connectivity [15].

This paper presents the vision to expand the openEO ecosystem by developing a ML API Specification for EO data cubes. The primary objective is to have a specification covering data pre-processing, managing training datasets, training ML models, making predictions, and mechanisms for saving and loading models. It shall support both classical machine learning and advanced deep learning techniques.

2 Core Components of the ML API

The proposed ML API shall be specifically designed to standardize and optimize the use of machine learning techniques in EO data applications, thereby facilitating reproducibility, reusability, and interoperability across various EO backend services. This comprehensive API covers all aspects of the ML workflow including data loading, data pre-processing, model training, parameter tuning, prediction, model saving and loading, smoothing, and uncertainty quantification.

The core API components include:

1. **Data Loading:** Users should be able to import EO data from a variety of sources and formats, specifically EO data that adheres to STAC standards, such as AWS Earth Data⁶. Furthermore, users should have the option to load training and in-situ data. Importantly, the training and in-situ data should comply with either ISO/DIS 19178-1 standard for Geographic Information—Training Data Markup Language for AI⁷, or the OGC Training Data Markup Language for AI (TrainingDML-AI)⁸, or the STAC-Label Extension specification⁹.

⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/earth/>

⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/89050.html>

⁸ <https://www.ogc.org/publications/standard/trainingdml-ai/>

⁹ <https://github.com/stac-extensions/label>

2. **Data Pre-processing:** For EO data cubes, several key pre-processing functions are essential. These include spatial resampling, temporal aggregation, re-projection, spatial and temporal filtering, cloud removal, and gap filling. Additionally, for training data, it is crucial to have the capability to filter data by time and space, to re-project, and to extract band values from EO data cubes.
3. **Model Training:** Model training involves using pre-processed data to train machine learning models, a critical step in developing predictive models capable of accurately analyzing EO data cubes. Key features of model training include the integration of a wide range of algorithms, such as classical machine learning methods like Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, and XGBoost, as well as deep learning techniques, including attention-based and CNN-based models. Batch processing to handle large datasets, cross-validation techniques to validate model performance and prevent overfitting, and the utilization of GPUs for faster training times, particularly for deep learning models, are also essential components.
4. **Model Parameter Tuning:** Systematic searching of model parameters is necessary to improve model performance, utilizing techniques such as grid search, and random search [20].
5. **Model Prediction:** The model prediction stage involves the utilization of a unified prediction function to apply trained models for making informed predictions on new data locations.
6. **Model Saving and Loading:** Saving and loading models allow for the persistence of trained models, enabling them to be reused without retraining. Important aspects include support for a common model serialization format, and ensuring interoperability so models can be easily transferred and deployed across various EO backend services and computing environments.
7. **Smoothing:** Smoothing techniques are essential for reducing noise and improving the clarity of EO data and model predictions. For instance, a single pixel might represent more than one desired output class. In a classification task, this can result in misclassified pixels due to mixed or ambiguous signals within a pixel. To address this, approaches like Bayesian smoothing are particularly valuable.
8. **Uncertainty Quantification:** Uncertainty quantification provides insights into the reliability and accuracy of model predictions, which is critical for making informed decisions based on EO data. Important features include probabilistic models for estimating prediction uncertainty, calculating and providing confidence intervals for predictions, model ensemble methods to improve prediction accuracy and quantify uncertainty.

This ML API will be a step to transform how scientists and EO professionals approach EO data cubes, instilling standardization while accommodating the flexibility needed for cutting-edge research and practical applications in environmental science and beyond.

Fig. 2. A representation of openEO-Compliant Backend Architecture for EO data cubes with ML API implementations.

3 Spatio-Temporal ML Model Cataloging

Developing a spatio-temporal ML models catalog is a crucial component of the standardized ML API framework designed for EO data cubes. This catalog will serve as a centralized repository to organize, document, and provide access to diverse ML models tailored for EO data cubes analysis. This initiative will make it simpler for researchers and EO professionals to discover and apply appropriate models to different EO tasks, thereby speeding up the development process and promoting the sharing of effective methodologies within the community.

The catalog will provide detailed metadata for each model, including its type, input, output, hyperparameters, distinct name, architecture, and intended applications. For example, a crop type classification model should not be used for tree species classification, a land cover model for Eastern Africa is unsuitable for Western Europe, and a model created using Sentinel 2 is not ideal for Landsat 8. The catalog will also incorporate version control to manage updates efficiently. Fully integrated with the ML API, it allows for seamless model loading into user workflows and supports the contribution of new models and updates.

The EO community must adopt a comprehensive standard for cataloging ML models tailored to EO data. This standard should address the unique spatio-temporal characteristics of EO data cubes, ensuring that models are effectively categorized, accessible, and adaptable to both classical machine learning models and state-of-the-art deep learning models. Currently, there are two STAC extensions available: the STAC ML-Model Extension¹⁰ and the more recent MLM

¹⁰ <https://github.com/stac-extensions/ml-model>

STAC Extension¹¹. The latter supports cataloging both classical ML and advanced DL techniques.

STAC has client libraries in popular programming languages within the EO community, such as Rstac [21] in R and Pystac¹² in Python. These libraries can be extended to allow users to query, access, and integrate ML models into their scripting workflows.

4 Challenges and Considerations

The development and implementation of standardized ML API and spatio-temporal models catalog in the field of EO encompass complex challenges and considerations that must be effectively managed to ensure success. Overcoming these barriers requires technical knowledge, strategic planning, and collaborative efforts.

A primary challenge is the need for a standardized approach for sharing ML training data for EO data cubes, including support for filtering, sampling, and selecting training data. Another critical aspect is the interoperability between popular ML frameworks like Torch¹³ and TensorFlow¹⁴, along with their various versions, across programming languages such as Python and R. This will allow the EO community to share models and integrate them into different EO back-end services. A common format, such as the Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX)¹⁵, is needed to facilitate this interoperability.

The new state-of-the-art DL methods developed for EO data cubes are complex and require extensive programming and DL expertise. These advanced approaches should be encapsulated in a simple API to democratize adoption and reuse within the EO community. Additionally, classical ML APIs often have different naming conventions for parameters across various libraries and their respective programming languages, which must be aligned for consistency and ease of use.

Model calibration presents another consideration, with a decision required on whether it should be conducted locally or in the cloud. This depends on factors, such as data accessibility, computational resources, security considerations, and collaboration requirements.

Classical ML methods, such as Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, and XGBoost, typically work with tabular data for inference and prediction. Therefore, it is crucial to outline the process of transforming EO data cubes into tabular formats. Handling training data spatial geometries, such as averaging values within polygons, is also essential for accurate model training and predictions.

¹¹ <https://github.com/stac-extensions/mlm>

¹² <https://github.com/stac-utils/pystac>

¹³ <https://pytorch.org>

¹⁴ <https://www.tensorflow.org>

¹⁵ <https://onnx.ai>

Moreover, in recent years, foundational models have emerged. These models are pre-trained on large, diverse datasets and can be adapted for different use cases across various data modalities. Examples of such models include Prithvi¹⁶[29], which is designed for multi-modal applications in Earth sciences, and the Swin Transformer¹⁷[28], a powerful model architecture known for its success in computer vision tasks. Incorporating foundational models into API workflows can unlock new capabilities for handling complex and diverse data sources effectively.

Lastly, it is beneficial to consider and learn from widely used ML libraries across various programming languages. Notable examples include mlr3 [23], caret [22], and tidymodels [24] in R, scikit-learn [26,27] in Python, MLJ [25] in Julia, and Keras¹⁸ in both R and Python.

5 Conclusion

Developing a standardized ML API integrated with spatio-temporal ML models catalog will transform the utilization and accessibility of EO data cubes. These advancements aim to simplify complex analytical processes, promote interoperability among different EO backend services and platforms, and cultivate a collaborative environment for sharing and innovation. By offering robust and user-friendly tools, these endeavors are positioned to expedite scientific research and practical applications across various fields including environmental monitoring, urban planning, and disaster response.

The successful adoption of these approaches has the potential to revolutionize EO data analysis, democratizing advanced ML techniques and making them more applicable and accessible. With a continued commitment to overcoming challenges and promoting widespread adoption, the standardization of ML API and model catalogs can become indispensable tools for EO professionals and researchers, advancing our comprehension and management of the planet's resources and challenges.

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¹⁶ <https://huggingface.co/ibm-nasa-geospatial/Prithvi-100M>

¹⁷ <https://huggingface.co/keras-io/swin-transformers>

¹⁸ <https://keras.io/>

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